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CRITICAL READING: A KEY COMPONENT FOR ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE

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Abstract. *Critical reading is essential for academic success, enabling students to analyze and evaluate information effectively. This review examines definitions and perspectives on critical reading, highlighting its role in developing logical and rhetorical skills. Research shows a strong link between critical reading abilities and academic performance, while also emphasizing its broader impact on individuals' understanding of information. Various techniques, such as role-playing and structured reading programs, are suggested to enhance critical reading skills. The review underscores the importance of supportive learning environments and the critical role of educators in fostering these abilities among students.*

Key words: *critical reading, academic success, logical skills, rhetorical skills, reading comprehension, educational initiatives, teaching techniques, meta-cognitive process, supportive, learning environments, student engagement.*

КРИТИЧЕСКОЕ ЧТЕНИЕ: КЛЮЧЕВОЙ КОМПОНЕНТ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКОГО ПРЕВОСХОДСТВА

Аннотация. *Критическое чтение необходимо для академических успехов, позволяя учащимся эффективно анализировать и оценивать информацию. В этом обзоре рассматриваются определения и взгляды на критическое чтение, подчеркивая его роль в развитии логических и риторических навыков. Исследования показывают тесную связь между критическими способностями к чтению и академической успеваемостью, а также подчеркивают ее более широкое влияние на понимание информации людьми. Для улучшения навыков критического чтения предлагаются различные методы, такие как ролевые игры и программы структурированного чтения. В обзоре подчеркивается важность благоприятной среды обучения и решающая роль преподавателей в развитии этих способностей среди учащихся.*

Ключевые слова: *критическое чтение, академический успех, логические навыки, риторические навыки, понимание прочитанного, образовательные инициативы, методы обучения, метакогнитивный процесс, поддерживающая среда обучения, вовлеченность учащихся.*

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Critical reading is a crucial precursor to academic success. Reading critically gives students the chance to consider and assess the information critically, which allows them to evaluate the situation they are in and perceive it from a wider perspective in connection with their critical comprehension. Using logical and rhetorical abilities is necessary for critical reading. Critical reading is vital because it enables to read and examine a text critically, dissecting it into its constituent pieces and assessing its strengths and weaknesses. It also help understand the author's intention for writing text and how it connects to real life. According to different relevant articles, scope of the topic will be discussed in this review.

Several authors have provided various kinds of definitions to define critical reading.

For example, Ozensoy (2021) defined that analyzing textual and visual content using objective standards, separating facts from views, asking questions, coming to logical conclusions, and doing comparisons and evaluations are all examples of critical reading. This definition is similar to that found in (Barnet & Bedau ,2011, as cited in Nguyen, 2020), who writes: critical readers are individuals who can precisely summarize arguments, recognize claims, find explicit or implied assumptions, analyze and assess the accuracy of the reasoning, and justify the usage of facts from a reading material. El-Hindi (1997, as cited in Karabay, 2015) gave similar concept to critical reading, “critical reading is a meta-cognitive process in which the reader interacts with texts, asks questions, makes predictions, makes connections via prior knowledge and experiences, breaks down prejudices, perceives hidden meanings and build new knowledge” (p. 2297).

Additionally, critical reading is an objective way of approaching to the any written work.

It is essential to conceive that critical reading is one of the important aspects to learn about for academic purposes. Kucheria et el. (2019, as cited in Dotson & Incera, 2022) stated that to be successful in academic contexts, critical reading is necessary. Academic success is strongly correlated with reading comprehension abilities. According to research by Karabay (2015), educational initiatives that included both critical reading and writing were more successful at improving students' academic performance. Similarly, Koray and Çetinkılıç (2020) concluded that teaching critical reading techniques was more successful in raising students' academic achievement than teaching in accordance with the curriculum. However, many university students struggle and take a long time to develop their critical reading skills, which is why so many of them are not proficient (Sultan et el., 2017, as cited in Nguyen, 2020). On the contrary, Alan and Amaç (2021) noted that critical reading abilities should not be valued solely academically. It is a skill that has a broad impact on people's lives. Any reader who does not have critical reading abilities

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may become ignorant of informatics as he or she reads. In order to make it easy and improve student's critical reading skills, various kinds of techniques and activities stated in the articles.

With the purpose of progressing critical reading skills on student's studying, different techniques are used. Jewett (2007, as cited in Zabihi & Pordel, 2011) used tactics like 'whose voice' and 'conversations with characters' to help pupils read critically. In the former, students were encouraged to consider which voices were heard (and which were not) in the stories, as well as what those voices may have said. In the latter, some students play the roles of the characters in the narrative, while other students pose questions to these fake individuals. By contrasting to above-mentioned technique, Ozensoy (2021) suggested more simple way of improving critical reading skills that Academic success test (AST) is applied as pre-test and post-test during the course in order to get an answer whether learners is using critical reading skill or not. Differently, for the instruction of effective reading, Zabihi and Pordel (2011) offer a list of guidelines. Their opinion is that a reading program should be created and used for a variety of reading objectives, from reading for informational purposes to reading to analyze texts. They assert that teaching students how to acquire and integrate a variety of reading methods, such as previewing, setting a purpose, forecasting, presenting questions, connecting to background knowledge, paying attention to text structure, guessing words from context, critiquing, and commenting on the text, is necessary for them to read well. It is also advised that students become proficient in a variety of text structures, such as those typical of newspapers, stories, reports, and other types of texts. Even though there were different kinds of strategies that were easy to use in the classroom, Nguyen (2020) tried to find another approaches. He mentioned that instructors could also put the questions in a Socratic quiz or a Socratic "space race" before or after reading tasks to help students enhance their comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and critical thinking skills. Moreover, the main requirement for fostering critical thinking in people from a young age is to create learning environments where students can debate ideas, voice their own opinions, and come up with several interpretations of the same event. This is due to the expectation that pupils' thinking abilities will not advance unless they are provided with material to consider, or are engaged in challenging and rewarding activities. Another crucial element that helps students develop critical reading is how teachers work within a structured educational framework, view, and exhibit critical thinking.

By examining different techniques to enhance critical reading skills, a role of teachers and learners in the classroom in the process of teaching should also be taken into consideration.

Students' roles in English Language Teaching (ELT) are influenced by the many roles that teachers play in the classroom. These roles are crucial for establishing the favorable settings that

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promote learning and direct the objectives that teachers have (Dotson & Incera, 2022). It is stated that if teachers want to enable students to take a more active part in the classroom, reflectively connecting their knowledge and perspectives with newly learned topics, they must forsake spoon-feeding education and give their students more flexibility to be active learners. Language teaching and learning practices used in the past may not be as effective in the ELT context as teachers hope for a variety of reasons, including the status of English as a global language, the early age at which young children learn English, getting a better job, technological innovations, and viewing English as the primary means of instruction at the university level. Nguyen (2020) added that students become learners that are more independent when they play the role of negotiators at various levels when working together and with the teacher. Teachers, on the other hand, are viewed as facilitators and organizers who control the communication process between students and the studied information and provide assistance when necessary. Similarly, Ozensoy (2021) claimed that when students participate in a variety of activities and collaborate, they learn at their own pace and ask critical questions of one another, which makes them more likely to learn best. He added that in student-centered classrooms, learning is more than just getting grades; it is about fostering learning since students have many opportunities to practice what they have learned and anticipate what will be on tests. However, using critical reading skills while reading and its effects may probably be based on students' level.

Reading can be defined differently depending on the level of the students: for beginners, it is primarily concerned with decoding and interpreting individual words, or it is an activity to learn aspects of pronunciation and speaking; however, in most cases, one reads a text in order to obtain the message or meaning intended by the author (Zabihi & Pordel, 2011). Reading was once thought to be a decoding activity, with the reader's job being to decode the message that the writer had encoded. However, the reader is not always able to decode the writer's encoded message, and he or she may even get a different meaning from the text because the reader and writer may not share a common assumption about a subject.

“The process of reading is different for different readers on different texts at different times and with different purposes” (Alderson & Bachman, 2000, as cited in Zabihi & Pordel, 2011).

Similarly, Koray and Çetinkılıç (2020) have distinguished between the goals of reading done at the high school level and the college level by stating that whereas college students read for increasing their logical thinking skills, high school kids read for facts, and this can only be done through critical reading. The reason for this difference is that readers have different schemas, and the author may have made various assumptions that the readers are unaware of. As opposed to

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reading, where there is no one to ask if they do not grasp anything, competent readers must engage in active interrogation of a book. As Nguyen (2020) mentioned that, one reason university students fail to realize their full potential in class is a lack of reading abilities. Because higher education classes involve a lot of reading, learning can become very abstract. A higher education student must develop abilities that are relevant to the associated reading task. Students' reading achievement can be identified through diagnostic. Students read content far too frequently as solitary facts. Certain items become difficult to recall. Rather, instruction is required for university students to grasp the relationship of content.

It is mentioned in the articles that type of text is also crucial while teaching reading critically. According to Zabihi and Pordel (2011), the difference between intensive and extensive reading is important as teaching reading. Reading carefully while concentrating on the linguistic elements required to understand the message is referred to as intensive reading.

These results are similar to those reported by (Karabay, 2015) that intensive reading is "approaching the text under the guidance of a teacher or a task that forces the student to focus on the text" (p.2299). On the other hand, extensive reading is a method of reading that is similar to that used by native speakers when reading in their own language; the learner reads at his own pace and level while searching directly for meaning. It involves reading a lot of information and longer texts repeatedly over a long period of time to gain a broad understanding. It can be done at home or in class (Goatly,2000, as cited in Karabay, 2015). By synthesizing different ideas about the influence of text types on reading, it is considered to be an investigation critical reading in reading texts.

In conclusion, critical reading is a very high level of knowledge of written materials involving interpretation and assessment skills that allow readers to discriminate between fact and opinion, separate important information from inconsequential one, and ascertain the writer's intent and tone. Moreover, reading with a critical eye entails responding to the text in a critical manner.

It is a process of connecting the reading's subject matter to one's own personal standards, values, and attitudes. It is the understanding of something that goes beyond what has been spoken, in other words. Finding facts and memorizing them are not the only goals of critical reading. It is the ability to read for one's own interests, utilizing one's faculties to better integrate one's experience of the outside world and to combine one's knowledge with that of others. This literature review has emphasized numerous academic sources by synthesizing: what actually critical reading is, several ways to improve critical reading skills, importance of it in academic success, and the role of teachers as well as type of texts in the process of teaching.

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